

“Exchange of car with little more cost” A Case of Pak Suzuki Motor Company Ltd. (PSMCL).

Author's Details: ⁽¹⁾ Muhammad Saqib Riaz ⁽²⁾ Mohsin Kiani

Project Supervisor- ⁽³⁾ Sir Numair Sulehri ⁽¹⁾⁽²⁾ Department of Management And Business Administration
Army Public College Of Management Sciences

Abstract

This case is about Pak Suzuki motor company limited manufacturer of Suzuki swift (auto). The sale of swift was low due to more cost as compared to others cars of Suzuki Company. To increase the sale of Suzuki Swift Company administration decides to provide customers the luxury car in exchange of small car with some additional lump sum amount

This case is about the incentives given to customers with large car at low price in exchange policy. It also focuses on the managerial decision making that how to foster the growth of Suzuki swift. Issue highlighted is important for management how to fulfill the need of customers.

Keywords: *Managerial decision making; exchange policy; automation;*

This case was written in 2014 by Muhammad Saqib Riaz and Mohsin Kiani, students of MBA. Army Public College of Management and Sciences RAWALPINDI.

It was 12'O clock at noon, In Suzuki Capital motors authorized dealership of PSMCL. Mr Waqas Sohail (Used car manager) and Mr. Waseem Satti (Sales Manager) was sitting together in their office having tea in front of them and discussing about less sale of Suzuki swift (automatic).

In the mean time peon of Mr. Waseem came in and stated that a customer named Capt. Jawad Ahmed came to meet sales manager to get his Suzuki mehran repaired from the company.

MR. Waseem (Sales Manager) went out to workshop to meet the customer and his car. Mr. Waseem conferred the repair of the Suzuki throughout whereas the customer was indented to get large car (Automatic) but due to more classy he was unable to buy it so he wanted to repair his Suzuki Mehran.

Suddenly Mr. Mohammad Waqas Sohail (Used Car Manager) also came and joined them in conversation. After heeded the issue of customer he suggested purchasing Suzuki swift (automatic) in exchange of his Suzuki mehran by paying an additional adequate amount.

Background

Suzuki Central Motors are a commissioned dealership of PSMCL. PSMCL is a neighborhood Suzuki auto manufacturing organization and offers different kinds of Suzuki auto to its customers all through the nation. The organization was secured in 1987. PSMCL has its wholesaler dealership everywhere throughout the nation and head office in Karachi.

The organization has a great budgetary quality in light of manufacturing amazing autos under license for Suzuki Motors Japan which is prestigious everywhere throughout the world. At beginning the organization began manufacturing of small autos and propelled in the neighborhood market which was real tempted by clients because of its amazing and low cost as contrasted with its competitors. The progress of the Suzuki Central Motors began flourishing.

Because of the disappointment of Liana, Pak Suzuki presented an alternate 1300cc auto in Jan 2009. The organization began production of Suzuki quick manual and hurled in the business. Swift has all the most recent peculiarities like force directing, focal locking, Auto Transmission and the ABS. The car was prevailing due to its low cost as compared to other companies with additional gimmicks of ABS Breaks. All the 1300cc autos in

Pakistan have worth range of Rs.1300, 000 to Rs.1400, 000, whilst Swift was propelled at Rs.99, 900. It has still advantage of price competition as compare to challengers of 1300cc cars in Pakistan.

Later on, the company began the manufacturing of Suzuki swift Automatic with liberal high price and launched it in the local market. The response from the local market is not bestowing to the desire of the company.

The Decision

Top management of PSMCL after receiving sales research report from the market about fewer sale of their recently launched Suzuki swift automatic had examined the matter to take a vital strategic decision. They decide to establish a used car department in which old cars from Suzuki will be exchanged with new cars from Suzuki after paying some additional cost.

This decision was conveyed to all dealerships of PSMCL. All the stakeholders were taken into confidence to make it triumph. The company also offers incentives to all dealers for Suzuki swift (auto) sale. The Capt. Jawad Ahmed came following 2 weeks, verbalized them that he had decided to assent their offer and would like to exchange his Suzuki mehran with new Suzuki swift by paying additional appropriate amount.

The Problem

In 2009 when Suzuki launched swift automatic, the reaction from the market was not up to the expectation of the company management.

The fundamental issue of the fewer sales was the high price of Suzuki swift Automatic as compared with other car manufacturing companies like Honda, Toyota. Individuals prefer to buy the luxurious cars of Honda Toyota as analogous to Suzuki swift. The brand equity of Suzuki cars is for small cars and less cost.

Discussion Questions

1. Analyze the company decisions of establishing used car department?
2. Was the decision implement by all Suzuki authorized dealership?
3. Was the decision resulted in increase of Suzuki swift automatic cars?

Teaching Notes

Synopsis

Pak Suzuki motor company limited manufactured liana Suzuki Swift car after detailed research and launched in the market, however the cost of the car was beyond the purchasing power of middle class customers. Moreover, high class customers prefer to purchase large cars of Honda, Toyota in a bit difference in price and more reliable with high re-sale value. So Mr. Waseem Satti of Suzuki central motors faced many difficulties in selling Suzuki Swift.

A customer Capt. Jawad Ahmed having Suzuki alto came in an authorized dealership of Suzuki motors for repairing purpose. The customer was not satisfy with the present car and desires to buy a swift but he had not enough money to buy his favorite car. Mr. Mohammad Waqas Sohail of used car department advised Capt. Jawad Ahmed to exchange his alto car from Suzuki motors by paying some additional amount.

Capt. Jawad Ahmed agreed the proposal and got Swift of his choice and Suzuki staff succeeded in fostering the sale growth of Suzuki Swift.

Teaching Objectives

This case focuses mainly focused of Suzuki liana car in competition with Honda and Toyota & its low sale in market

The case may be use full for the students to comprehended the following

- Importance of establishment of used car department
- Importance of involvement of all steak and stock holders
- Role of management in successful running of used car department
- Increase in sale of automatic car by better strategy

Suggested Answers to Discussion Questions

1. Analyze the company decisions of establishing used car department?

To foster the sales growth of Suzuki swift Mohammad Waqas Sohail gave an opportunity to his customer to exchange his car by making additional payment..Due to this decision it strength the position of company and to retain their loyal customers.

2. Was the decision implement by all Suzuki authorized dealership?

Yes, and it helped to increase the sales. The used car dept focused to sale the used car in used car expo by making necessary maintenance.

3. Was the decision resulted in increase of Suzuki swift automatic cars?

Yes, as swift was introduced with automatic system. The customer who needs luxury car can exchange their car by making additional payment. As other Honda and city are expensive than Suzuki.

Tips for Case Analysis

The instructor should encourage the students for discussion and brainstorming on following aspects of the case:

- Identify the issue.
- Discus different courses of action to solve the problem.
- Students to analyze the decision.
- Students can also be asked to discuss the role of management at company level & at distributors level.

References: